

Supramolecular Enzyme Engineering in Complex Nanometer-Thin Biomimetic Organosilica Layer

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Abstract: The use of enzymes in industrial processes is often hampered by their limited stability under operational conditions. As enzymes' function and stability are directly correlated to their three-dimensional structure, numerous methods aiming at the preservation of this structure have been developed. While stabilization can be achieved using solid scaffolds for encapsulating the enzyme, it often results in loss of enzymatic activity owing to a lack of conformational mobility of the biocatalyst. With the idea of mimicking protein-protein interactions to create a network of weak force interactions between the surface of an immobilized enzyme and a synthetic protective layer, we have developed a chemical strategy allowing the use of complex mixtures of building blocks mimicking the lateral chain of natural amino acids. After crosslinking a model enzyme at the surface of silica nanoparticles, incubation with eight different organosilane mixtures allowed growing protective organosilica layers of controlled thicknesses. The nanoparticles produced were characterized by scanning electron microscopy and their biocatalytic activity was measured under a series of operational stress conditions. Our results clearly demonstrated that increasing the complexity and biomimetic nature of the protection layer allowed for a relevant improvement of the protection effect. Indeed, when compared with the basic formulation, selected complex formulations allowed for an improvement of up to 100 % when treated at 50°C for 60 min or in the presence of a denaturing detergent (SDS).

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The need for robust enzymes is growing at a fast pace concomitantly with the increasing interest, especially of the pharmaceutical industry, in swapping traditional batch chemical syntheses by bio-based continuous processes.¹⁻³ The main challenges to be faced are converging towards the design of highly stable enzymes that are immobilized on a solid support to allow their retention in a compartment through which the reaction mixture is flowed. Regarding stability improvement, besides screening approaches,³ molecular biology provides a set of tools that allows improving, through genetic engineering, the properties of enzymes in terms of stability and resistance to external stresses.³⁻⁵ In contrast, supramolecular enzyme engineering refers to a concept of enzyme modification without manipulating the protein sequence by genetic engineering or covalent modification of the biomolecule. It aims at improving the capabilities of enzymes in terms of stability and resistance to external stresses and to ultimately tune the biocatalytic properties of enzymes.

Besides enzyme protection, the use of enzymes for continuous production requires their retention by immobilization on solid components.^{3,6-9} Additionally, immobilization often positively affect enzyme stability. Among a large choice of possible carrier materials including polymers, metals, titanium and zirconia, silicates are of particular interest.^{6,10-12} Besides the fact that they represent an inexhaustible source of raw material, silica has several decisive chemical advantages. Indeed, silicon, being tetravalent, possesses a bonding geometry similar to that of carbon and is prone to form large covalent networks. However, the chemical reactivity of silicates is different from that of organic molecules and targeted chemical modifications of silica are straightforward in hybrid organic-inorganic systems.¹³⁻¹⁵

Besides sol-gel methods to produce silica-protein hybrids,^{16,17} scientists produced silica-enzyme hybrids following biomimetic syntheses. Indeed, by mimicking the natural process of biosilicification,¹⁸ a number of enzymes have been successfully entrapped in silica matrices.¹⁹⁻²¹ Nevertheless, since silica is inherently negatively charged, it cannot create a shell finely surrounding the whole surface of the protein and establish chemical interactions with the exposed amino acids.²²

Working on the development of protein-recognition nanomaterials, we demonstrated that viruses or virus-like proteins could serve as templates to grow an organosilica layer at the surface of the virus capsid.^{23,24} We expanded recently this approach to a series of enzymes belonging to different classes and having different molecular weights (from 98 kDa to 472 kDa) and demonstrated that the assembly/polycondensation of simple building blocks allows producing a soft protective layer providing the enzyme with a remarkable stability against stress conditions (i.e., pH, temperature, chaotropes, ultrasounds and protease).²⁵ This protective effect was attributed to the interactions

between the protective shell and the surface of the enzyme. In the present manuscript, we describe the design of complex organosilica shells, aiming to increase the number of interactions points between the shielding organosilica and the protein surface. The general synthetic procedure reported herein consists of two main steps: enzyme crosslinking on the surface of silica nanoparticles and enzyme shielding in an organosilica layer produced through the polycondensation of different organosilane mixtures. We used organosilanes (OS) building blocks sharing chemical similarities with natural amino acids, hydroxymethyl-triethoxysilane (**H**); propyl-triethoxysilane (**P**); aminopropyl-triethoxysilane (**A**) and benzyl-triethoxysilane (**B**) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Chemical formulas of tetraethyl-orthosilicate (**T**), hydroxymethyl-triethoxysilane (**H**), propyl-triethoxysilane (**P**), aminopropyl-triethoxysilane (**A**) and benzyl-triethoxysilane (**B**).

Materials and methods

General

Tetraethyl orthosilicate [TEOS (**T**), $\geq 99\%$], (3-aminopropyl)triethoxysilane [APTES (**A**), $\geq 98\%$], ammonium hydroxide (ACS grade, 28-30%), ethanol (ACS grade, anhydrous), glutaraldehyde (Grade I, 25% in water), *o*-nitrophenyl- β -D-galactopyranoside (ONPG) and β -galactosidase (β -gal) from *Kluyveromyces lactis* were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Switzerland).

Protein Assay Dye Reagent Concentrate was purchased from Bio-Rad. Hydroxymethyltriethoxysilane (**H**), 50% in ethanol, *n*-propyltriethoxysilane (**P**) and benzyltriethoxysilane (**B**) were purchased from ABCR (Germany). All chemicals were used without further purification. A volume of 10 mL β -gal were dialysed against 2 L dialysis buffer (100 mM phosphate, 5 mM MgCl_2 , 100 mM NaCl, pH 6.5) using a SnakeSkin dialysis tube (10K MWCO) at 4°C for 24 h. Nanopure water (resistivity $\geq 18 \text{ M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$) was produced with a Millipore Synergy purification system. Silica nanoparticles (SNPs) were prepared using the previously published procedure.²³

Enzyme shielding

In a typical synthesis experiment, 18 mL of 3.2 mg mL⁻¹ of SNPs in water were reacted with 11 μ L (0.047 mmol) of A for 30 min, in 20 mL glass vials under stirring (400 rpm) at 20 °C. The particle suspension formed was centrifuged at 3220 x g for 10 min and the pellet re-suspended in nanopure water. After repeating this procedure (hereinafter called “washing cycle”) once more, particles were incubated during 30 min in 18 mL of 0.1% (v/v) aqueous glutaraldehyde solution. After two washing cycles with nanopure water, the resulting pellets were suspended in 18 mL of MES buffer (MES 10 mM, 5 mM MgCl₂, pH 6.2) and reacted, at 20°C, with β -gal (at 0.1 mg mL⁻¹) for 1 h under magnetic stirring. Subsequently, TEOS was added and allowed to react for 1 h (Table 1). In order to produce particles with the different silane mixtures (A-T, A-T-H, A-T-P, A-T-B, A-T-P-B-H, A-T-P-B, A-T-P-H, A-T-B-H) respectively, the following organosilanes were added sequentially to the reaction mixture as reported in Table 1. The silane polycondensation reaction was stopped after 22 h by washing the particles in buffer (100 mM potassium phosphate, 5 mM MgCl₂, pH 6.5). SNPs were then suspended in buffer, maintained at 25°C for increasing durations and finally stored at 4°C. Particle size measurement was carried out on SEM micrographs acquired at a magnification of 150,000 X using the @analySIS software package.

	T (mmol)	A (mmol)	H (mmol)	P (mmol)	B (mmol)
A-T	0.392	0.090			
A-T-H	0.242	0.090	0.150		
A-T-P	0.242	0.090		0.150	
A-T-B	0.242	0.090			0.150
A-T-P-B- H	0.242	0.090	0.050	0.050	0.050
A-T-P-B	0.242	0.090		0.075	0.075
A-T-P-H	0.242	0.090	0.075	0.075	
A-T-B-H	0.242	0.090	0.075		0.075

Table 1: Composition of the different organosilanesilane mixtures used for the production of protection layers.

Scanning electron microscopy and particle size measurement

Particles were imaged using a Zeiss SUPRA® 40VP scanning electron microscope. A 2 μ L drop of each sample was spread on freshly cleaved mica substrates, dried at 37°C, and sputter-coated with a gold-platinum alloy for 15 s at 10 mA. Micrographs were acquired using the InLens mode with an accelerating voltage of 20 kV. Particle sizes were measured on micrographs acquired at a magnification of 150,000 X (Figure 1) using the @AnalySIS software package. One hundred measurements were carried out for each sample.

Determination of enzyme immobilization yield

The β -gal immobilization yield was calculated by measuring the quantity of unbound enzyme remaining in the supernatant after binding. A bovine serum albumin standard curve was prepared in MES buffer (MES 10 mM, 5 mM MgCl_2 , pH 6.2). Fifty μL of Protein Assay Dye Reagent Concentrate were added to 200 μL of sample or albumin solution, mixed and incubated for 5 min at 20°C. Two hundred μL of sample were added into a 96-well plate and the absorbance was measured at 595 nm (Synergy™ H1 Hybrid reader from BioTek).

Enzymatic assay and kinetic studies

The catalytic activity of immobilized and shielded β -gal was determined by measuring the *ortho*-nitrophenyl- β -D-galactopyranoside (ONPG) hydrolysis at 40°C under shaking at 650 rpm in a Thermomixer (Eppendorf). In a typical β -gal activity assay, 190 μL of ONPG (21 mM) in buffer (100 mM potassium phosphate, 5 mM MgCl_2 , pH 6.5) were equilibrated at 40°C for 5 min. Ten μL of sample were added and incubated for 5 min at 40°C under 650 rpm shaking. To deactivate the enzyme and stop the reaction, 200 μL of 1 M Na_2CO_3 were added. In order to remove the SNPs, samples were centrifuged for 1 min at 10 000 rpm. The amount of the *ortho*-Nitrophenol produced was determined by measuring the absorbance at 420 nm of 200 μL solution. The catalytic activities were calculated using the molar extinction coefficient of *o*-nitrophenol ($\epsilon_{420\text{nm}} = 4300 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) extracted from a standard curve.

Catalytic parameters, maximum velocity and Michaelis-Menten constant (V_{max} and K_m , respectively), were measured performing a typical activity assay with increasing ONPG quantities (at final concentrations 0.5-20 mM respectively). V_{max} and K_m were extracted from the double reciprocal (Lineweaver-Burke) plot.

Thermal stress test

A sample of 200 μL of SNP were incubated at 50°C for 60 min under shaking at 650 rpm. Aliquots of 10 μL were collected every 10 min, added to 190 μL of ONPG (21 mM) in buffer (100 mM potassium phosphate, 5 mM MgCl_2 , pH 6.5) and measured for hydrolytic activity at 40°C as described above.

Chaotropic stress test

A volume of 190 μL of ONPG (21 mM) in buffer (100 mM potassium phosphate, 5 mM MgCl_2 , pH 6.5) containing 6.6 M urea or 1.1% SDS respectively, were equilibrated for 5 min at 40°C. Ten μL of SNP were added and the catalytic activity was measured as described above.

Results and discussion

The overall nanobiocatalyst production strategy is schematized in Figure 1. After cross-linking the enzyme at the surface of amino-modified SNPs using glutaraldehyde, the particles were incubated with a mixture of OS.

Scheme 2: Schematic representation of the chemical strategy of enzyme shielding at the surface of silicon dioxide. SNP surface (in grey) is amino modified by incubating the particles suspension with APTES. Afterwards, in order to provide anchoring residues for the enzyme, the amino-modified particles are crosslinked with the homo-bifunctional cross-linker glutaraldehyde. a) The enzyme (E) is anchored at the surface of SNPs; b) The immobilized enzyme is incubated with a mixture of different silanes (red, grey, pink and purple shapes represent the different silanes of the mixture). Depending on the functional groups of the silanes and on the amino acids present on the surface of the enzyme, non-covalent interactions established between the surface of the protein and the inner shell of the protective layer; c) A biomimetic shell is formed through the silanes polycondensation

In order to produce enzyme shielding layers allowing to establish a large set of interactions with the surface of immobilized enzymes, we used a series of formulations of OS building blocks mimicking natural amino acids. For all formulations tested, we kept the total amount of silanes (in mole) constant. **A** and **T** are present in all mixtures; **T** is a precursor of inorganic silica and is able to establish four covalent bonds with its neighbouring building blocks, it is necessary to produce stable organosilica. The amine functions of **A** is known to have a catalytic effect on the polycondensation of OSs.²⁶ Besides reacting with other organosilane molecules to form siloxane bonds, the amine group of **A**, being positively charged at neutral pH, can form ionic bonds with the superficial anionic amino acids of the protein. The choice of other OSs (**H**, **P** and **B**) is justified by the different properties of their functional groups: the hydroxyl group of **H** mimics polar aminoacids (e.g., serine, threonine), **P** and **B** serve as aliphatic and aromatic building blocks mimicking leucine and phenylalanine respectively. The polycondensation was allowed during 22 hours at 20°C. Afterwards, the nanobiocatalysts were isolated, washed and imaged by means of field-emission scanning

microscopy (SEM) and a statistical analysis of the diameter of the produced particles was carried out (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Representative SEM micrographs of untreated SNP and β -gal protected with biomimetic shells produced with A-T, A-T-H, A-T-P, A-T-B, A-T-P-B-H, A-T-P-B, A-T-P-H, A-T-B-H; scale bars represent 100 nm.

From Figure 1, it could be seen that while the starting SNPs possessed a smooth surface, the SNPs where the enzyme was immobilized and shielded exhibit a relatively rough surface. This roughness could be attributed to the presence of the protein at the surface of the SNPs. Indeed, β -gal is a large tetrameric protein complex with a tri-axial ellipsoid shape with dimensions of $15.9 \times 9.3 \times 5.3$ nm. When comparing the different protection layer composition, no major differences could be seen. Additionally, the thickness of the external layer also showed a limited dependence on the OS mixture composition with a value of 25 ± 3 nm. We have previously demonstrated that hybrid protein-organosilica layer produced with A and T are undergoing, at room temperature, a curing reaction resulting in an increase in activity of the shielded enzyme over time.²⁵ In order to assess the effect of the layer composition on this curing reaction, we measured the catalytic activity of the types of nanobiocatalysts produced in the function of the curing time at 25°C (1, 3, 5, 7, 8 and 10 days) using the conventional *o*-nitrophenyl- β -galactoside (ONPG) assay (Figure 2). From Figure 2a, it could be seen that for all tested compositions, the evolution of enzymatic activity followed a similar trend, with

an initial fast increase of the catalytic activity during the first day and a plateau reached after 4-6 days. Besides this general trend, obvious differences due to the layer composition could be noticed. Indeed, while the lowest activity of $10 \text{ nmol}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ at the end of the curing reaction is measured for the **A-T** layer, a substantial increase is measured for layers produced with **A-T-P-H**, **A-T-P**, **A-T-P-B**, **A-T-H** and **A-T-P-B-H** with values of 24, 27, 36, 39, and $40 \text{ nmol}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The highest catalytic rates were obtained for **A-T-B** and **A-T-B-H** with values of 53 and $66 \text{ nmol}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

In order to rule out the possibility that the increase in activity measured was due to a change in the physico-chemical properties of the shielding layer inducing differential mass transfer of the substrate, we investigated the Michaelis Menten kinetics for the different produced nanobiocatalysts (Figure 2b).

Figure 2: (a) Recovery of the enzymatic activity of β -galactosidase protected with shells of different composition during 10 days of curing (A-T-B-H: \diamond ; A-T-B: \triangle ; A-T-P-B-H: \bullet ; A-T-H: \square ; A-T-P-B: \circ ; A-T-P: \blacktriangle ; A-T-P-H: \blacklozenge ; A-T: \blacksquare). (b) Substrate (ONPG) hydrolysis catalyzed by β -galactosidase protected with shells of different composition after 10 days of curing.

While the maximum velocity of the enzyme was affected by the chemical composition of the layer, the apparent Michaelis-Menten constant remained mainly unchanged and comparable to that of the soluble enzyme (4 mM) (Figure 3). This undoubtedly indicated that the diffusion of the substrate was not hindered

by the shielding layer and that the differences in biocatalytic activities could be attributed to changes in the nano-environment of the enzyme.

Figure 3: V_{max} (white bars) and K_m (black bars) measured after 10 days of curing.

In order to assess the effect of the chemical composition of the layer on its protective effect, we submitted the nanobiocatalysts produced to different stress conditions, namely temperature, surfactant (sodium dodecyl sulfate, SDS) and chaotrope (urea); the results are presented in Figure 4 and 5.

Figure 4: Relative activity of β -gal shielded with different shells measured after increasing incubation time at 50°C (A-T-B-H: \diamond ; A-T-B: \triangle ; A-T-P-B-H: \bullet ; A-T-H: \square ; A-T-P-B: \circ ; A-T-P: \triangle ; A-T-P-H: \blacklozenge ; A-T: \blacksquare).

The thermal stress was carried out by incubating nanobiocatalysts produced at 50°C over a period of 60 min. While after 15 min of incubation, samples A-T-H, A-T-P, A-T-P-B-H and AT lost more than 50% of their initial activity, samples A-T-B, A-T-P-B, A-T-P-H and A-T-B-H preserved as much as 60%, 62%, 51% and 55% activity,

respectively. After 30 min all the samples lost more than 50% activity with exception of A-T-P-B which preserved 51%. After 45 min, samples A-T-H, A-T-P-H and A-T lost more than 70% of their initial activity while A-T-P, A-T-B, A-T-P-B-H, A-T-P-B and A-T-B-H preserved more than 30% of their initial activity. Finally, after 60 min, only A-T-B and A-T-P-B preserved more than 30% of their initial activity. This overall improvement of stability may be explained by the confinement of the enzyme in the protective shell, as demonstrated for enzymes encapsulated in polymer nanopores²⁷ or inorganic materials.²⁸ The effect of the organosilica layer against chaotropic stresses using urea (6 M) and sodium dodecylsulfate (1%) was also studied. The activity was measured directly in denaturing conditions. In the case of urea, all the samples preserved as much as 20% of catalytic activity compared to the untreated samples (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Relative activity of β -gal shielded with different shells measured in presence of 6 M urea (grey bars) or 1% SDS (black bars).

Oppositely to thermal stabilization, the layer composition did not seem to influence the stability of the enzyme to urea. Irrespective of the shell composition, samples preserved only 20% about of activity, which is nevertheless fairly high when considering that a 6 M urea treatment is typically denaturing proteins. Additionally, it is known that urea, because of its ability to bind through hydrogen bonding to the active site of β -gal, has a inhibitor effect.²⁹ Therefore, one can assume that the decrease in catalytic activity is not due (at least totally) to enzyme denaturation but rather to a competition between the enzyme substrate and urea to bind the amino acids of the catalytic pocket. Indeed, being the protective shell porous, small molecules such as urea or the enzyme substrate can reach the catalytic site of the enzyme. In the present study, the loss in biocatalytic activity may be at least partially attributed to this inhibition effect. In the case of the SDS (1%) treatment, the nanobiocatalyst **A-T** preserved 30% of activity. While samples **A-T-B**, **A-T-P-B-H**, **A-T-P-B**, **A-T-P-H** and **A-T-B-H**

preserved 40% around of the initial activity, samples **A-T-H** and **A-T-P** preserved 45% and 53% of the initial activity. This set of results demonstrated that although SDS is in contact with the enzyme, the protective shell prevents the protein denaturation. Indeed, being the enzyme “shielded” and finely surrounded by the organosilanes, it does not unfold like it would for a soluble enzyme. Moreover, a strong influence of the layer composition on the stability of the shielded enzyme against SDS denaturation is undoubtedly demonstrated.

The biomimetic organosilica layer produced by the self-assembly/polycondensation of different OSs not only brings a comfortable nano-environment in which the enzyme preserves its catalytic activity but also provides a protective shell against different stresses such as heat and chaotropes. Due to the multipoint interactions between the OSs and the amino acids of the protein, the biomimetic organosilica layer allows preservation of the three-dimensional conformation of the enzyme.

Conclusions

In summary, we have developed a strategy of supramolecular enzyme engineering allowing the improvement of enzyme resistance to various stress conditions. The strategy is based on the possibility to mimick the general interaction occurring between proteins and to obtain an accurate enzyme shielding in a biomimetic organosilica layer. We have demonstrated the large influence of the chemical composition of the protective layer in the biocatalytic activity of the biocatalysts. The reported method of enzyme shielding is versatile and can be applied to all enzymes. Since the number of commercially available OS building blocks is quite large, the composition of the OS formulation can be fine tuned to on the basis of the chemical properties of the chosen enzyme. Supramolecular enzyme engineering paves the way toward the development of new smart catalytic materials that shall find application in various industrial fields.

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